

THE INFLUENCE OF STRONG ELECTROLYTES AND MERCURIC CHLORIDE ON THE CONDUCTIVITY OF AQUEOUS BENZOIC ACID.

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Alfred Tingle (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, **31**, 792) was perhaps the first to make accurate measurements of the electrical conductivity of benzoic acid in aqueous solutions. The conductivity of such a weak acid in the presence of electrolytes has been studied by various investigators. Pouchon measured the conductivity of phosphoric acid in the presence of its salts (*Radium J.*, 1908, **5**, 167). Boeseken and Verkade (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1916, **36**, 167) studied the influence of oxalic acid on the conductivity of aqueous boric acid. Kendall and Andrews (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 1545) from solubility measurements found that the solubility of benzoic acid is depressed due to HCl added, and that the conductivity of HCl is reduced by benzoic acid. McBain and Kam (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1332) studied the effect of a number of neutral salts on a weak organic acid like acetic acid, by vapour pressure measurements. Kolthoff and Bosh (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1927, **46**, 430) observed that these salts decrease the H-ion activity in dilute HCl solutions but at higher concentrations have the reverse effect. Meer Wien (*Annalen*, 1927, **455**, 227) observed an increase in the ionisation of weak electrolytes by complex formation. Kolthoff (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1928, **47**, 861, 872) showed that neutral salts increase the activity of undissociated acid; the constant K is not increased, in close agreement with the results obtained by Guntelberg and E. Schildt (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, **133**, 393). The influence of neutral salts on acids, with special reference to catalysis in solutions, has been discussed by Dawson (*Proc. Leeds Phil. Soc.*, 1929, **1**, 491). Larson (*Syensk. Kem. Tidsks.*, 1929, **41**, 130) has studied the effect of strong electrolytes on the distribution of acetic acid between water and an organic solvent like benzene, ether, etc. The activity coefficients of benzoic acid, the benzoate ion, in the presence of neutral salts, have been studied from κ , M , F and solubility measurements by various investigators.*

* Chase and Kilpatrick (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 2589; 1931, **53**, 1732); Larson (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, **153**, 466; 1931, **153**, 299; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, **196**, 354; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, **157**, 342); Kolthoff and Bosch (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 1685, 1695, 1702).

Recently a number of investigators† have determined the dissociation constant K of benzoic acid at 25° from conductivity and solubility measurements, which show K to be variable in the range 6.295×10^{-5} to 6.7×10^{-5} . The value recorded in this paper is 6.24×10^{-5} (cf. Table I) which is very near the results of Saxton and Meir (*loc. cit.*). Data are given to show the influence of different concentrations of LiCl, NaCl, KCl, RbCl, CsCl, HCl, BaCl₂ and HgCl₂. The inclusion of HgCl₂ was suggested by observation of some of its rather remarkable and anomalous behaviour as a coagulant (cf. Joshi and Kulkarni, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 439; Joshi and Menon, *ibid.*, 1937, 14, 103; Joshi and Ramdas, *ibid.*). It might also be added that some unpublished work by Mr. Haldhar and one of us from these laboratories showed a depression, in numerous cases, of the partition coefficient of benzoic acid between toluene and water in the presence of the electrolytes. This might be due to (a) an increase in the ionisation of benzoic acid in the aqueous phase, (b) a "salting-out effect", (c) alteration of such factors as the solubility, dielectric constant and therefore the dissociating power of the medium. The addition of the electrolyte would also affect the degree of the polymerisation of the solvent (Subramann and Breyer, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1933, B, 20, 17, 53). It was of interest, therefore, to examine the above possibilities by studying the conductivity of aqueous benzoic acid in presence of the series of electrolytes mentioned above.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The conductivity determinations of benzoic acid in presence of the electrolytes—LiCl, NaCl, KCl, RbCl, CsCl, BaCl₂, HCl and HgCl₂ of Kahlbaum's guaranteed extra pure chemicals were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The containers were all of high resistance Jena glass. The conductivity cell, used, was of Pyrex glass; with the platinum electrodes, each of 1 sq. cm. area, fixed vertically, the inter-electrode distance being 1.2 cm. The bridge employed for the determination of electrolytic resistances was Pye's modified Post Office Box of dial resistance type; a small Kohlrausch's induction coil was used as an A.C. generator. The conductivity water used for experiments was prepared by distilling twice distilled water in a silica distiller and collecting only the middle fraction. This stock of water which was used for

† Brockmann and Kilpatrick (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1483); Vogel and Jeffery (*Chem. Ind.*, 1934, 53, 779; *Phil. Mag.*, 1934, vii, 18, 902); Saxton and Meir (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1928).

making the various solutions was examined every now and then for its constancy of conductivity, the specific conductivity being 1.878×10^{-6} mhos. The cell constant was determined every now and then by using freshly prepared $N/50$ -KCl solution at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The electrodes with fresh platinised surfaces were always kept immersed in conductivity water after the completion of an experiment.

Table I gives the values for the conductivities of benzoic acid for different concentrations ($N/50$ to $N/1200$). For calculating the value of α , the degree of ionisation, the value for the equivalent conductivity (Λ_∞) of benzoic acid at infinite dilution is taken to be 381.3 mhos. The values for K , the dissociation constant, are recorded in the last column.

In Tables II to XXI are recorded the values for the conductivities of the mixture of benzoic acid and each of the electrolytes mentioned above. The strength of the mixture in terms of its components, benzoic acid and the electrolyte, is recorded in column 1; the concentrations of the components are expressed for the system *after mixing*. Columns 2 and 3 give respectively the resistance in ohms for the mixed solutions and that for varying concentrations of the electrolyte, measured for the corresponding concentrations of the electrolyte present in the mixture as shown in column 1. In column 4 are given the specific conductivities in mhos for the mixtures; in column 5 are given the specific conductivities for the corresponding concentrations of the electrolyte. In column 6 are given the values for the specific conductivity of benzoic acid obtained by subtracting the specific conductivity of the electrolyte (column 5) from that of the mixture as given in column 4. The specific conductivity of pure benzoic acid is given at the bottom of column 6 in Table II. This scheme has been followed in the subsequent tables.

Tables II—III show the influence of LiCl in the range $N/64$ — $N/4096$ for $N/100$ and $N/200$ -benzoic acid. Tables IV-VI refer to NaCl whose concentration was varied over the above range in the presence of $N/100$, $N/150$ and $N/200$ benzoic acid. Tables VII—IX refer to KCl, the concentrations of both benzoic acid and KCl being the same as in the previous case. Tables X—XIII refer in the same way to RbCl and CsCl. Tables XIV—XVI refer to the use of BaCl_2 , XVII and XVIII of HCl and XIX—XXI to that of HgCl_2 .

In drawing the curves, shown in Figs. 1, 2, 3, the square roots of the normalities of each of the above electrolytes (except in the case of HgCl_2 , Fig. 3) have been plotted along the abscissae; the corresponding specific conductivities of the benzoic acid in the mixture, as calculated by difference, are shown along the ordinates.

TABLE I.

Conductivities of benzoic acid soln. at 25 + 0.1°.

Strength of acid.	Resistance.	Conductivity Sp.	Conductivity equiv.	Degree of ionisation.	Dissoc. const. K.
N/50	899.0	0.0004154	20.77	0.05449	6.28×10^{-5}
N/100	1279.0	0.0002913	29.13	0.07640	6.32
N/200	1853.0	0.0002011	40.22	0.1055	6.222
N/400	2695.0	0.0001382	55.28	0.1450	6.13
N/75	1107.0	0.0003367	25.25	0.06623	6.269
N/150	1594.0	0.0002337	35.06	0.09196	6.21
N/300	2306.0	0.0001616	48.48	0.1272	6.174
N/600	3329.0	0.0001120	67.16	0.1762	6.277
N/1200	4899.0	0.00007605	91.27	0.2394	6.279
				Mean	6.24×10^{-5}

TABLE II.

Mixture of N/100-benzoic acid and LiCl at 25° ± 0.1°.

No.	Composition.	Resistance of mixture.	Resistance of LiCl only.	Specific conductivity of mixture.	Specific conductivity of LiCl only.	Specific conductivity of N/100-benzoic acid calc. from diff.		
1	N/100	N/64	195.3	232.6	0.001931	0.001622	0.0003090	
2	Benzoic acid	Lithium chloride	N/128	332.5	452.0	0.001116	0.0008332	0.0002828
3			N/256	523	892.0	0.0007201	0.0004211	0.0002990
4			N/512	736.5	1743.0	0.0005107	0.0002144	0.0002963
5			N/1024	930.0	3418.5	0.0004041	0.0001082	0.0002949
6			N/2048	1075.5	6680.0	0.0003491	0.00005424	0.0002949
7			N/4096	1165	12850.0	0.0003221	0.00002709	0.0002951
8			only.					0.0002913

In the tables Resistance (R) has been expressed in ohms, and Conductivity (sp. and equiv.) in mhos.

TABLE III.

Mixture of N/200-benzoic acid and LiCl.

Cell constant = 0.3777.

No.	Composition.		R. of mixture.	Specific conductivity of mixture.	N/200-acid calc. from diff.
1	N/200	N/64	205.1	0.001839	0.0002173
2	"	N/128	361.6	0.001042	0.0002090
3	Benzoic acid	N/256	597.0	0.0006306	0.0002095
4	"	N/512	896.0	0.0004195	0.0002051
5	"	N/1024	1198.0	0.0003132	0.0002050
6	"	N/2048	1456.0	0.0002574	0.0002032
7	"	N/4096	1618.0	0.0002314	0.0002043
8	" only.				0.0002011

TABLE IV.

Mixture of N/100-benzoic acid and NaCl.

No.	Composition.		Resistance of mixture		Specific conductivity of mixture.		
				NaCl only.		NaCl only.	N/100-acid calc. from diff.
1	N/100	N/64	177.4	205.6	0.002126	0.001835	0.0002910
2	"	N/128	307.45	399.0	0.001226	0.000946	0.0002816
3	Benzoic acid	N/256	490.0	777.6	0.0007689	0.0004839	0.0002850
4	"	N/512	703.4	1536.5	0.0005351	0.0002440	0.0002911
5	"	N/1024	913.2	3004.0	0.0004117	0.0001239	0.0002878
6	"	N/2048	1062.0	5895.0	0.0003538	0.00006223	0.0002916
7	"	N/4096	1158.0	11200.0	0.0003243	0.00003189	0.0002924
8	" only.						0.0002913

TABLE V.

Mixture of N/150-benzoic acid and NaCl

No.	Composition.		R. of mixture.	Specific conductivity of		
				mixture.	N/150-acid calc. from diff.	
1	N/150	N/64	182.3	0.002070	0.0002350	
2	"	N/128	321.9	0.001171	0.0002266	
3	Benzoic acid	Sodium chloride	N/256	529.0	0.0007121	0.0002282
4			N/512	755.4	0.0004790	0.0002350
5			N/1024	1053.4	0.0003566	0.0002327
6			N/2048	1268.0	0.0002960	0.0002358
7			N/4096	1402.0	0.0002677	0.0002338
8	" only.				0.0002337	

TABLE VI.

Mixture of N/200-benzoic acid and NaCl.

No.	Composition		R. of mixture.	Specific conductivity of		
				mixture.	N/200-acid calc. from diff.	
1	N/200	N/64	185.2	0.002037	0.0002020	
2	"	N/128	331.3	0.001136	0.0001936	
3	Benzoic acid	Sodium chloride	N/256	558.0	0.0006751	0.0001912
4			N/512	845.5	0.0004448	0.0002008
5			N/1024	1159.5	0.0003242	0.0002003
6			N/2048	1420.0	0.0002642	0.0002037
7			N/4096	1590.5	0.0002356	0.0002037
8	" only.				0.0002011	

TABLE VII.

Mixture of N/100-benzoic acid and KCl.

No.	Composition.		Resistance of		Specific conductivity of		
			mixture.	KCl.	mixture.	KCl only.	N/100-acid calc. from diff.
1	N/100	N/64	152.1	172.9	0.002481	0.002183	0.0002980
2	"	N/128	268.0	337.2	0.001407	0.001118	0.0002890
3	"	N/256	440.0	665.0	0.0008563	0.0005660	0.0002903
4	"	N/512	653.2	1318.0	0.0005763	0.0002846	0.0002917
5	"	N/1024	867.5	2604.0	0.0004334	0.0001431	0.0002903
6	"	N/2048	1036.0	5114.0	0.0003627	0.00007198	0.0002907
7	"	N/4096	1142.0	9825.0	0.0003288	0.00003656	0.0002923
8	N/100-acid only.						0.0002913

TABLE VIII.

Mixture of N/150-benzoic acid and KCl.

No.	Composition.		R. of mixture.	Specific conductivity of	
				mixture.	N/150-acid calc. from diff.
1	N/150	N/64	155.0	0.002434	0.0002510
2	"	N/128	278.7	0.001353	0.0002350
3	"	N/256	471.6	0.0007990	0.0002330
4	"	N/512	727.0	0.0005176	0.0002330
5	"	N/1024	996.0	0.0003772	0.0002341
6	"	N/2048	1221.0	0.0003074	0.0002354
7	"	N/4096	1378.0	0.0002721	0.0002356
8	N/150-acid only.		0.0002337

TABLE XI.

Mixture of *N*/200-benzoic acid and RbCl.

No.	Composition.		Resistance of mixture.	Specific conductivity of mixture.	conductivity of <i>N</i> /200-acid calc. from diff.	
1	<i>N</i> /200	<i>N</i> /128	277·2	0·001361	0·0002045	
2	„	<i>N</i> /256	477·9	0·0007885	0·0002070	
3	Benzoic acid	Rubidium chloride	<i>N</i> /512	751·0	0·0005011	0·0002074
4			<i>N</i> /1024	1063·0	0·0003535	0·0002036
5			<i>N</i> /2048	1354·0	0·0002771	0·0002026
6			<i>N</i> /4096	1565·0	0·0002395	0·0002021
7	<i>N</i> /2000-acid only.	0·0002011	

TABLE XII.

Mixture of *N*/100-benzoic acid and CsCl.

No.	Composition		Resistance of		Specific conductivity of			
			mixture.	CsCl only.	mixture.	CsCl.	<i>N</i> /100-acid calc. from diff.	
1	<i>N</i> /100	<i>N</i> /128	261·2	325·5	0·001445	0·001158	0·0002870	
2	„	<i>N</i> /256	425·4	645·4	0·0008860	0·0005832	0·0003025	
3	Benzoic acid	Caesium chloride	<i>N</i> /512	638·3	1275·0	0·0005899	0·0002941	0·0002955
4			<i>N</i> /1024	850·5	2488·5	0·0004422	0·0001499	0·0002923
5			<i>N</i> /2048	1019·0	4945·0	0·0003690	0·00007456	0·0002944
6			<i>N</i> /4096	1131·0	9648·0	0·0003321	0·00003731	0·0002948
7	<i>N</i> /100-acid only.	0·0002913		

TABLE XV.

Mixture of N/150-benzoic acid and BaCl₂.

No.	Composition.		R. of mixture.	Specific conductivity of	
				mixture.	N/150-acid calc. from diff.
1	N/150	N/64	176.8	0.002134	0.0002240
2	"	N/128	309.9	0.001216	0.0002263
3	Benzoic acid	Barium chloride N/256	508.9	0.0007401	0.0002316
4	"	N/512	750.0	0.0005016	0.0002432
5	"	N/1024	1028.0	0.0003656	0.0002337
6	"	N/2048	1247.0	0.0003010	0.0002338
7	N/150-acid only.		0.0002337

TABLE XVI.

Mixture of N/200-benzoic acid and BaCl₂.

No.	Composition.		R. of mixture.	Specific conductivity of	
				mixture.	N/200-acid calc. from diff.
1	N/200	N/64	177.5	0.002125	0.0002150
2	"	N/128	318.0	0.001186	0.0001963
3	Benzoic acid	Barium chloride N/256	526.0	0.0007169	0.0002064
4	"	N/512	809.0	0.0004650	0.0002068
5	"	N/1024	1109.0	0.0003387	0.0002068
6	"	N/2048	1393.0	0.0002692	0.0002020
7	N/200 acid only*		0.0002011

TABLE XVII.

Mixture of N/100-benzoic acid and HCl.

No.	Composition.		Resistance of		Specific conductivity of		
			mixture.	HCl only.	mixture.	HCl only.	N/100-acid calc. from diff.
1	N/100	N/64	58.3	58.5	0.006475	0.006453	0.00002200
2	"	N/128	114.0	115.2	0.003311	0.003276	0.00003500
3	"	N/256	221.1	228.2	0.001707	0.001653	0.00005350
4	"	N/512	406.6	456.6	0.0009272	0.0008252	0.0001020
5	"	N/1024	650.5	908.0	0.0005789	0.0004141	0.0001648
6	"	N/2048	883.9	1819.0	0.0004255	0.0002058	0.0002197
7	"	N/4096	1050.0	3698.0	0.0003578	0.0001010	0.0002568
8	N/100-acid only.		0.0002913

TABLE XVIII.

Mixture of N/200-benzoic acid and HCl.

No.	Composition.		R. of mixture.	Specific conductivity of	
				mixture.	N/200-acid calc. from diff.
1	N/200	N/64	58.8	0.006421	-0.00003200
2	"	N/128	115.0	0.003282	+0.000006000
3	"	N/256	228.0	0.001655	+0.000001500
4	"	N/512	432.6	0.0008712	+0.000004600
5	"	N/1024	742.8	0.0005065	0.00009238
6	"	N/2048	1162.5	0.0003408	0.0001350
7	"	N/4096	1408.0	0.0002665	0.0001655
8	N/200-acid only.		0.0002011

TABLE XIX.

Mixture of *N*/100-benzoic acid and $HgCl_2$.

No.	Composition.		R. of mixture.	Specific conductivity of			
	<i>N</i> /100	0.25 <i>N</i>		mixture.	$HgCl_2$ only.	<i>N</i> /100-acid calc. from diff	
1		0.25 <i>N</i>	819.8	0.0004586	0.0001649	0.0002937	
2	"	0.1875	880.3	0.0004271	0.0001379	0.0002892	
3	"	0.1406	932.0	0.0004032	0.0001191	0.0002841	
4	"	0.1054	980.0	0.0003834	0.0001021	0.0002813	
5	Benzoic acid	Mercuric chloride	1018.0	0.0003692	0.00008873	0.0002805	
6			1056.0	0.0003558	0.00007736	0.0002785	
7			1093.0	0.0003437	0.00006847	0.0002753	
8			1119.0	0.0003358	0.00006060	0.0002752	
9			1139.0	0.0003299	0.00005353	0.0002764	
10			1161.0	0.0003235	0.00004761	0.0002759	
11			<i>N</i> /100-acid only.	0.0002913

TABLE XX.

Mixture of *N*/150-benzoic acid and $HgCl_2$.

No.	Composition.		R. of mixture.	Specific conductivity of		
	<i>N</i> /150	0.25 <i>N</i>		mixture.	<i>N</i> /150-acid calc. from diff.	
1		0.25 <i>N</i>	955.0	0.0003936	0.0002287	
2	"	0.1875	1038.0	0.0003621	0.0002242	
3	"	0.1406	1104.4	0.0003403	0.0002212	
4	"	0.1054	1174.5	0.0003199	0.0002178	
5	Benzoic acid	Mercuric chloride	1222.0	0.0003073	0.0002186	
6			1268.0	0.0002961	0.0002188	
7			1318.5	0.0002849	0.0002165	
8			1352.0	0.0002777	0.0002171	
9			1375.0	0.0002730	0.0002195	
10			1413.5	0.0002656	0.0002180	
11			<i>N</i> /150-acid only.	0.0002337

TABLE XXI.

Mixture of N/200-benzoic acid and HgCl₂.

No.	Composition.		R. of mixture	Specific conductivity of mixture	N/200-acid calc. from diff.	
1	N/200	0.25 N	1075.0	0.0003494	0.0001845	
2	"	0.1875	1160.0	0.0003238	0.0001859	
3	"	0.1406	1252.0	0.0002999	0.0001808	
4	"	0.1054	1316.0	0.0002855	0.0001834	
5	Benzoic acid	Mercuric chloride	0.07911	1385.0	0.0002769	0.0001822
6			0.05933	1448.0	0.0002592	0.0001819
7			0.04450	1497.0	0.0002507	0.0001823
8			0.03338	1551.0	0.0002420	0.0001814
9			0.02503	1600.0	0.0002345	0.0001810
10			0.01878	1631.0	0.0002300	0.0001824
11			N/200-acid only.

TABLE XXII.

Mixture of N/100-benzoic acid after mixing at 25 ± 0.1°.

Conc. of HCl in the mixture.	Degree of ionisation for N/100-benz. acid in presence of HCl	Reduced sp. conduct of N/100-benz. acid.	Sp. Conducty. of N/100-benz. acid calc. from diff.
C.	a.		
N/64	0.00410	0.0000156	0.0000220
N/128	0.00798	0.0000304	0.0000350
N/256	0.0152	0.0000583	0.0000535
N/512	0.0275	0.000105	0.000102
N/1024	0.0429	0.000163	0.000165
N/2048	0.0565	0.000215	0.000220
N/4096	0.0655	0.000250	0.000257
0	0.0764	0.000291	0.000291

TABLE XXIII.

Temperature = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

I	2	3	4	For N/100-Benzoinic acid.			For N/150-Benzoinic acid.			For N/200-Benzoinic acid.		
				5	6	4'	5'	6'	4''	5''	6''	
Conc. of HgCl ₂ in Hydrolysis mixture.	% H ⁺ in mixture.	Conc. of HgCl ₂ in litre	Degree of ionisation in presence of HgCl ₂ .	Reduced sp. conductivity in mhos.	Sp. conduct. calc. from diff. in mhos.	Degree of ionisation in presence of HgCl ₂ .	Reduced sp. conductivity in mhos.	Sp. conduct. calc. from diff. in mhos.	Degree of ionisation in presence of HgCl ₂ .	Reduced sp. conductivity in mhos.	Sp. conduct. calc. from diff. in mhos.	
0.25 N	0.12	0.00030	0.0633	0.000241	0.000294	0.0738	0.000188	0.000229	0.0817	0.000196	0.000185	
0.1875	0.14	0.000263	0.0648	0.000247	0.000289	0.0758	0.000193	0.000224	0.0844	0.000161	0.000186	
0.1406	0.17	0.000239	0.0657	0.000250	0.000284	0.0772	0.000196	0.000221	0.0861	0.000164	0.000181	
0.1054	0.20	0.000212	0.0669	0.000254	0.000281	0.0788	0.000200	0.000218	0.0882	0.000168	0.000183	
0.07911	0.23	0.000182	0.0681	0.000259	0.000280	0.0805	0.000205	0.000219	0.0904	0.000172	0.000183	
0.05933	0.27	0.000158	0.0692	0.000263	0.000279	0.0821	0.000209	0.000219	0.0924	0.000176	0.000182	
0.0445	0.31	0.000138	0.070	0.000267	0.000275	0.0833	0.000212	0.000217	0.0940	0.000179	0.000183	
0.03338	0.37	0.000124	0.0706	0.000269	0.000275	0.0842	0.000214	0.000217	0.0953	0.000182	0.000181	
0.02503	0.43	0.000108	0.0713	0.000272	0.000276	0.0853	0.000217	0.000219	0.0965	0.000184	0.000181	
0.01878	0.51	0.0000958	0.0718	0.000274	0.000276	0.0861	0.000219	0.000218	0.0975	0.000186	0.000183	
0	0.0764	0.000291	0.000291	0.0920	0.000234	0.000234	0.106	0.000201	0.000201	

DISCUSSION.

These results for the conductivity of aqueous benzoic acid in the presence of LiCl, NaCl, KCl, RbCl, CsCl, BaCl₂, HCl and HgCl₂, in their various concentrations, show, that except in the case of the last two substances (*cf.* Tables XVII—XXI, Fig. 3), the additive law holds; the specific conductivity of the mixture equals the sum of the specific conductivities of the two components, each determined separately. The absence of any alteration in the specific conductivity of a weak acid like benzoic acid in the presence of the above salts (except HgCl₂) even at low concentration (*cf.* Tables II—XVI, last column) as shown by the almost horizontalness of specific conductivity— $\sqrt{\text{concentration}}$ curves in Figs. 1 and 2 is interesting. The results

FIG. 1.

of numerous investigators on "the neutral salt effect", which is ordinarily shown rather markedly by weak acids suggests an increase in H⁺ concentration or rather, in H⁺ ion activity and therefore in the corresponding dissociation constant. McBain and Kam (*loc. cit.*) find evidence to the contrary.

They argue that the electrical potential of a hydrogen electrode is determined by the product of the chemical potential and H^+ ion concentration, *i.e.*, its activity. The experimental fact, *viz.*, that the potential of a hydrogen electrode is increased in an aqueous solution of a weak acid in the presence of a neutral salt indicates an increase in H^+ ion activity. McBain and Kam (*loc. cit.*) make an interesting postulate, *viz.*, that concomitantly with the last quantity, the activity of the undissociated molecules in the system is increased. They adduced the experimental support for this in the

FIG. 2.

observation that the vapour pressure of acetic acid and therefore its activity is actually increased by the presence of a neutral salt like NaCl. The mass

law expression in terms of the various activities for the ionisation equilibrium of such a weak acid in the presence of a neutral salt should therefore be unaltered, since the activities of both the undissociated acid and H^+ are affected equally. This leads to the result that the corresponding degree of dissociation and therefore the specific conductivity of the above acid would remain unaltered, despite the presence of the neutral salts. Our results on benzoic acid (Tables II-XVI, Figs. 1, 2) are in agreement with this deduction. The work of Chase and Kilpatrick (*loc. cit.*), Larson (*loc. cit.*) and Kolthoff and Bosch (*loc. cit.*) on the activity measurements of benzoic acid in the presence of the neutral salts (whose concentration was varied over a wide range) by *x. m. f.* and solubility methods has shown that the activity of undissociated benzoic acid molecules increases remarkably by the above additions.

The results for the specific conductivity of benzoic acid at $N/100$ and $N/200$ in the presence of hydrochloric acid in the range $N/64$ to $N/4096$ show that the above quantity is diminished in the presence of the latter. That this can be ascribed to a substantial extent to the common ion effect is shown by the results in Table XXII. Assuming that for any of the values of C , the concentration of hydrochloric acid employed, α' its degree of ionisation is unity, α , the corresponding degree of dissociation for benzoic acid in its presence is given by the equation

$$\left(C\alpha' + \frac{\alpha}{V} \right) \cdot \alpha = K(1 - \alpha),$$

where K is the dissociation constant of benzoic acid. These calculated values for α corresponding to various values of C for $N/100$ -benzoic acid are shown in the 2nd vertical column in Table XXII. From a knowledge of α , Λ^∞ , and the dilution for benzoic acid, the reduced specific conductivity for benzoic acid can be calculated. These values are also shown in the above table. Its last column gives the corresponding experimentally found values for benzoic acid in the presence of hydrochloric acid. Comparison of the last two columns shows that the agreement between the calculated and observed values is satisfactory. Similar results were obtained for $N/200$ benzoic acid.

Results on the influence of $HgCl_2$ given in Tables XIX-XXI show that the specific conductivity of benzoic acid is diminished in its presence. This diminution at a given concentration of benzoic acid is sensible only at large dilutions of $HgCl_2$. Now it is known that $HgCl_2$ is hydrolysed, thus giving

free HCl in aqueous solutions. Ley (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, 30, 249) has given data for the degree of hydrolysis of HgCl_2 in the range $N/16$ to $N/256$; from these the degrees of hydrolysis for the dilutions used in this work were obtained by extrapolation and are shown in the 2nd column in Table XXIII, on the assumption that the degree of hydrolysis approaches zero as dilution tends to zero, which is substantially correct. From the data of Luther (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 943) for example, for the proportions of the various

FIG. 3.

molecular and ionic species in 0.26 M- HgCl_2 at 25°, the H^+ ion concentration seems to be negligibly small. The H^+ ion concentrations at these various

dilutions are shown in the 3rd column, α , the degree of dissociation of benzoic acid in the presence of these H^+ being calculated from the above equation. In the same way the corresponding reduced (*i.e.* corrected for hydrolysis) specific conductivity of $N/100$ - benzoic acid was calculated. These two quantities are shown in the 4th and 5th columns ; 6th column gives the actual value in the mixture *obtained by difference*. Similar calculations were made for $N/150$ - and $N/200$ -benzoic acid; columns 4', 5', 6' and 4'', 5'', 6'' refer to them respectively, in Table XXIII. An examination of the results under columns 5, 6; 5', 6'; 5'', 6'' shows clearly that the common ion effect arising out of the hydrolysis of $HgCl_2$, is one factor leading to a diminution in specific conductivity of benzoic acid. On this basis, it is to be anticipated that in strong solutions of $HgCl_2$ corresponding to minimum hydrolysis, the common ion effect would be a minimum; it follows, therefore, that the specific conductivity of benzoic acid, obtained by difference would approach that of aqueous benzoic acid in the absence of a disturbing electrolyte. An examination of the results under the above columns show that the above deduction is in accord with the facts.

The results for the specific conductivity corrected for hydrolysis depart from those obtained by difference or by the additive law in the case of strong solutions of $HgCl_2$. This discrepancy might arise, possibly from the fact that extrapolation made on the assumption, *viz.*, negligibility of hydrolysis at very high concentrations, is not rigorously accurate, *i.e.*, it indicates more hydrolysis than what obtains under the conditions.

It might now be pointed out that in the above discussion of the results, a tacit assumption has been made that a weak acid like the benzoic would not affect the conductivity due to any of these substances examined in this work, *i.e.*, would not influence the molecular or the ionic reactivity characteristic of each of the added materials. In the case of $HgCl_2$, however, it would appear that this is not strictly true, which agrees with the fact that $HgCl_2$ stands apart from the rest of the substances examined in having some of the properties of a *weak electrolyte*. It is appreciably likely that this hydrolysis is sensibly suppressed by the presence of benzoic acid. Simms (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 745) has shown some evidence for the possible inactivation of a weak electrolyte in the presence of another. Sufficient data are not available in the literature for deducing such an effect from the current theories for the activity of a "weakly" ionised material. That the above possibility in the case of the hydrolysis of $HgCl_2$ is in agreement with experimental facts is suggested by an examination of data in Table XXIII. It is seen that the divergence from the specific conductivity of benzoic acid deduced from the additive law, of its conductivity, when

corrected for hydrolysis of HgCl_2 is greater, the greater the concentration of benzoic acid, which suggests that since the extrapolation is a common factor, the above hydrolysis is affected (suppressed) by benzoic acid.

S U M M A R Y.

1. The mean value obtained for the dissociation constant of benzoic acid at 25° is 6.24×10^{-5} , in close agreement with the recent values.
2. The specific conductivity of aqueous benzoic acid, whose concentration was varied in the range $N/100-N/200$, in the presence of the electrolytes— LiCl , NaCl , KCl , RbCl , CsCl , BaCl_2 , HCl and HgCl_2 , whose concentration was varied in the range $N/64-N/4096$, was determined, at 25° .
3. The additive law for the specific conductivity of the mixture of benzoic acid and electrolyte holds good especially in dilute solutions, except in the case of HCl and HgCl_2 , where the specific conductivity is less than that given by the additive law. This has been ascribed to the common ion effect in the former and due to hydrolysis of the latter.
4. Evidence is also adduced to show a possible suppression on the hydrolysis of HgCl_2 by the benzoic acid.

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